

1 **Plant Disease Phenomics to Support Breeding of Robust** 2 **Crops**

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23 **ABSTRACT**

24 Phenotyping of plant disease remains a major bottleneck for breeding, variety testing, and
25 crop management. While visual scoring has long been standard, advances in high-resolution
26 imaging and computer vision offer great potential for more scalable and standardized
27 quantification of disease under field conditions. This review synthesizes progress in image-
28 based phenotyping of visible disease to support breeding of robust crop varieties. We frame
29 robustness through the complementary mechanisms of resistance, escape, and tolerance, and
30 we discuss how image-based phenomics can contribute to their quantitative assessment in the
31 field. We focus on the challenges of scalable field deployment, including contact-free imaging,
32 symptom diagnosis and localization, and canopy-level quantification under complex field
33 scenarios. We highlight the importance of integrating disease phenotyping with phenology
34 monitoring, 3D canopy reconstruction, and epidemiological and functional–structural plant
35 modelling to move from descriptive disease quantification toward a mechanistic understanding
36 of seasonal epidemics and their effects on yield.

37 INTRODUCTION

38 **Background**

39 Deploying robust crop varieties that maintain yield and quality under disease pressure is
40 widely considered the most durable, cost-effective, and environmentally safe approach to
41 disease mitigation. However, identifying robust genotypes remains a major bottleneck as it
42 requires extensive field testing (92, 93, 141), making it difficult to collect phenotypic data with
43 the detail, precision, accuracy, and throughput needed to support comprehensive selection
44 decisions. While genotyping has become affordable, comparable gains in phenotyping remain
45 far behind, leaving genomic information underutilized for breeding (12, 49, 137).

46 To overcome this bottleneck, rapid, non-invasive sensing techniques for disease detection,
47 diagnosis, and quantification have been developed. Different sensor modalities including RGB
48 (Red, Green, Blue), multi- or hyperspectral, thermal, and chlorophyll fluorescence imaging
49 have been applied at scales from individual lesions to field canopies, with each sensor modality
50 targeting specific aspects of a host's response to infection (129).

51 Non-RGB approaches often focus on pre-visual detection (23, 114, 149), characterization of
52 symptom-level host-pathogen interactions (71, 86), and assessment of distinctive host
53 responses to infection to support diagnosis (30, 85). In contrast, RGB-based approaches are
54 limited to visible signs of disease but offer the major advantage of producing inexpensive, high-
55 resolution images which can be directly interpreted by plant pathologists. Consumer-grade
56 cameras and smartphones now routinely provide 20 to 100 megapixels, facilitating the
57 collection of large high-quality image data sets at low cost.

58 End-to-end trainable deep learning (DL) models have played a critical role in RGB image
59 interpretation by enabling the extraction of complex, multiscale disease-relevant visual features
60 beyond simple color cues. In pioneering work, Mohanty et al. (90) demonstrated their potential
61 to identify crops and associated diseases from RGB images of diseased leaves. Since then, DL
62 based on expert-annotated imagery has enabled the localization, diagnosis, quantification, and
63 phenotypic characterization of plant disease symptoms in RGB images that align closely with
64 traditional visual assessments (65, 102, 152). This technology holds substantial promise for
65 enabling precise, standardized, and high-throughput quantitative disease assessment under field
66 conditions, with direct relevance for breeding, variety testing, and crop management.

67 **Motivation and scope of the review**

68 Numerous studies have addressed pre-visual detection, employing diverse sensors and
69 analytical approaches, as summarized elsewhere (20, 24, 81, 83, 129). In practice, breeders

70 typically seek to track disease progression, producers rely on visual symptom-based thresholds
71 to guide interventions, and epidemiologists aim to model and predict epidemics. Within these
72 contexts, pre-visual detection often provides limited actionable insight. We therefore focus on
73 quantifying visible symptoms. Important exceptions where pre-visual detection can directly
74 inform management decisions include quarantine pathogens (149) or pathogens threatening
75 food safety (82).

76 Substantial work has sought to optimize DL models, typically through architectural
77 modifications or training strategies such as transfer learning and data augmentation. Yet,
78 increasingly powerful and general-purpose models for image interpretation are emerging at a
79 rapid pace, suggesting that hand-engineering neural network architectures for optimal
80 performance on small, task-specific datasets may be of limited long-term value (132). We
81 therefore focus instead on applications and challenges specific to disease phenotyping,
82 highlighting key opportunities and challenges along the entire workflow, from raw data
83 acquisition to comprehensive genotype characterization.

84 The review is grounded in three concurrent developments:

- 85 (i) **From controlled-environment screening to in-field evaluation.** Image-based disease
86 phenotyping is evolving from tissue- and organ-level assessments under controlled
87 conditions toward canopy-level measurements in the field. While laboratory and field
88 approaches sometimes target the same traits, they are not interchangeable. The choice
89 of a phenotyping strategy must be guided by the target traits and pathosystem
90 characteristics, with the biological interpretation of results depending critically on
91 experimental context.
- 92 (ii) **From diagnosis to large-scale quantitative disease assessments.** Recent work has
93 largely emphasized disease diagnosis, yet in agronomic practice, the primary bottleneck
94 lies in robust and scalable quantitative assessment. Despite its central importance for
95 resistance breeding, precision agriculture, and epidemiology (27, 28, 83), the potential
96 of RGB imaging for this purpose remains underexplored.
- 97 (iii) **From single-disease phenotyping to a holistic field phenomics approach.** Parallel
98 advances in RGB-based crop phenotyping increasingly enable dynamic monitoring of
99 growth and phenology, plant morphology and canopy architecture, as well as yield
100 component formation under field conditions (11, 113, 115, 154). Integrating such
101 contextual information with spatially and temporally explicit disease assessments
102 represents a major opportunity to improve our understanding of canopy-level host-

103 pathogen interactions that determine the trajectory of seasonal epidemics and the impact
104 of diseases on crop performance.

105 Our review first outlines a conceptual ideotype of genotype robustness under disease pressure
106 that serves as a unifying framework, then examines which phenotypic information is required
107 to characterize specific components of disease robustness. By synthesizing recent advances
108 across scales and experimental settings, we highlight key conceptual and methodological gaps
109 and propose directions to align disease phenotyping with practical decision-making in breeding,
110 variety testing, and commercial crop production.

111 **THREE PILLARS OF DISEASE ROBUSTNESS**

112 Factors determining the robustness of a genotype under disease pressure may be broadly
113 classified into three categories (Supplementary Figure 1; 94, 99, 103). **Disease escape** enables
114 a host to avoid pathogen infection because genetically encoded factors prevent the pathogen
115 from coming into direct physical contact with susceptible host tissues. **Disease resistance**
116 increases the host's ability to restrict pathogen establishment, development, and reproduction
117 once the pathogen has come into direct physical contact with host tissues. **Disease tolerance**
118 minimizes yield and quality losses resulting from disease. We note that neither these
119 categorizations nor these definitions are universally accepted (e.g., 94, 105, 143). However,
120 these common definitions provide a useful conceptual framework, because the underlying
121 candidate traits and mechanisms differ fundamentally among categories, leading to distinct
122 phenotyping requirements.

123
124 *Supplementary Figure 1 Graphical representation of particular forms of escape, resistance, and tolerance. ‘++’ and ‘--’ denote*
125 *high level and low level of expression, respectively. Escape: Larger distances between leaves reduce spore dispersal (arrows)*
126 *in the vertical canopy, reducing contact of upper leaves with pathogen spores. Resistance: With all else equal, disease-related*
127 *damage is reduced. Tolerance: The impact of a given intensity of disease on yield and quality (here thousand kernel weight) is*
128 *reduced. Illustrations of wheat plants were modified from Schürch et al. (118).*

129 Disease resistance is essential for the development of robust cultivars and has received by
130 far the most attention. Ideally, however, breeding strategies should aim to integrate escape and
131 tolerance with resistance, as these mechanisms act largely independently, complement one
132 another, and provide insurance when any single strategy fails (77, 92, 97, 98, 101). Their overall
133 impacts are optimized when combined: for example, escape characteristics are particularly
134 effective under low to moderate epidemics, but may be overcome by strong epidemics (1, 44).
135 Each strategy offers specific advantages that can mitigate disadvantages of another. For
136 example, while genetic resistance is easier to assess and has more predictable effects, it can lose
137 its effectiveness due to pathogen evolution, and is often specific to certain diseases. In contrast,
138 disease escape and tolerance are less predictable, but are also less prone to pathogen adaptation
139 and are more likely to be broadly effective against multiple diseases (26, 141). Thus, combining
140 resistance with escape and tolerance traits can enhance the overall robustness of a crop
141 genotype, helping it maintain performance across diverse environments and against rapidly
142 evolving pathogen populations. Separate assessments are needed to maximize progress for each
143 mechanism individually: for example, without accounting for the effects of escape, estimates
144 of resistance can be significantly biased (74, 110).

145 The remainder of this review follows this conceptual framework. For each disease mitigation
146 strategy (escape, resistance, and tolerance), we summarize the current knowledge of its genetic,
147 molecular, physiological, and mechanistic basis and outline the associated phenotyping
148 requirements, with a particular focus on the extent to which RGB imaging can address these
149 needs.

150 **RESISTANCE**

151 **Genetic, molecular, and physiological basis**

152 Plant disease resistance is commonly categorized into major-gene resistance (MGR) and
153 quantitative resistance (QR). Major resistance genes against biotrophic pathogens typically
154 encode proteins that trigger a localized hypersensitive response upon detection of a pathogen
155 effector. Similar mechanisms underlie strong single-gene mediated defense reactions against
156 necrotrophic pathogens, primarily by limiting stomatal penetration rather than inducing
157 hypersensitivity (22), which can result in slower and more quantitative resistance reactions (88,
158 126). While MGR is highly effective, it is often isolate-specific and, like fungicides, exerts
159 strong directional selection that can rapidly diminish its effectiveness (38).

160 In contrast, QR usually arises from the combined action of many genes with small additive
161 effects (93, 99, 100, 120). QR does not prevent infection but slows epidemic development, for

162 example by reducing infection frequency, lesion expansion, spore production, or by extending
163 the latency period (62, 70, 99, 120). Collectively, these ‘components of QR’ (141) decrease the
164 pathogen’s multiplication rate and increase the time required by the pathogen to complete its
165 lifecycle. Therefore, QR is also referred to as rate-reducing resistance.

166 In many pathosystems, MGR and QR are not strictly separable. For example, resistance to
167 *Septoria tritici* blotch in wheat is highly quantitative at the field level (67), reflecting the genetic
168 diversity of natural pathogen field populations, the strain-specific partial effectiveness of
169 individual major resistance genes (88), and the deployment of multiple resistance genes within
170 cultivars (32). These factors contribute to complex, polygenic resistance phenotypes, even when
171 individual components follow a gene-for-gene model.

172 Whether MGR or QR dominates pathogen-plant interactions depends largely on scale and
173 context. Seedling assays using single pathogen strains under highly conducive greenhouse
174 conditions mainly expose the effects of major resistance genes, obscuring weaker components
175 of resistance. In contrast, field evaluations with diverse pathogen populations across several
176 growth stages and under fluctuating environmental conditions typically reveal more complex,
177 quantitative, and dynamic outcomes. These approaches provide complementary insights, but
178 are not interchangeable. Accordingly, we review disease phenotyping across scales and contexts
179 of observation, contrasting organ- or symptom-level assessments under highly controlled
180 conditions with field evaluations representative of the target environment.

181 **Controlled-environment phenotyping of pathogen-plant interactions**

182 Resistance or susceptibility reactions following the gene-for-gene model often result in a
183 bimodal distribution of phenotypes, reflecting pronounced susceptibility or near-complete
184 immunity. End-point visual assessment of symptom presence or absence is fast and provides a
185 straightforward and objective readout of pathogen-plant compatibility. Nevertheless,
186 limitations in throughput, phenotypic detail captured, the ability to understand temporal
187 dynamics through repeated assessments, and in precision and accuracy have been noted. These
188 can be addressed using image-based phenotyping, as described next.

189 **Throughput.** Limitations in throughput are often noted (i) in quantitative genetics studies
190 that evaluate large panels of host and pathogen genotypes, (ii) when tracking disease
191 development through repeated measurements over time, and (iii) when aiming for detailed
192 symptom characterization. In these cases, the volume, frequency, and precision requirements
193 can exceed what can be achieved by manual scoring.

194 Attempts to increase throughput have focused on image acquisition and trait extraction from
195 images. One notable attempt is a robotic system proposed by Lück et al. (78) which automates

196 the repeated imaging of inoculated leaf segments. On a larger scale, conveyor-belt phenotyping
 197 systems may facilitate whole-plant monitoring (4). A system proposed by Thomas et al. (131)
 198 enables automated imaging of field-like canopies under controlled conditions, using an
 199 automatic sensor positioning system. Beyond these examples, most efforts have focused on
 200 incremental improvements in image acquisition and processing by relaxing standardization
 201 requirements and enabling parallel imaging of more samples (41, 45, 78, 87, 152).

202 Though essential, these advances are insufficient on their own to enable high-throughput
 203 assessments of pathogen-plant interactions. Throughput in phenotyping is commonly defined
 204 as the number of experimental units that can be processed per working hour (58), with the most
 205 important objective being to match the scale at which germplasm can be genotyped (12, 49,
 206 137). In that respect, gains obtained by the aforementioned systems remain elusive, because the
 207 primary bottlenecks lie not in image capture and analysis, but in the labor-intensive steps of
 208 growing plants and pathogens, performing inoculations, tracking inoculated material, and
 209 preparing it for standardized imaging. We argue that these approaches should be consistently
 210 referred to as precision phenotyping rather than high-throughput phenotyping systems (87, 147,
 211 152). No systems providing true end-to-end high throughput along the entire phenotyping
 212 workflow are currently available. Given the complexity and diversity of the operations
 213 involved, breakthroughs cannot be expected soon.

214
 215 *Figure 1 Conceptual framework for phenomics-enabled decomposition of quantitative resistance (QR) into component traits*
 216 *for trait-based selection. Field-expressed QR is a complex, canopy-level dynamic trait reflected in a reduced rate of epidemic*
 217 *development (C). Linking this target trait to underlying component traits could improve breeding efficiency. Static traits*

218 *measurable from single snapshots, such as lesion phenotypes indicating resistance or susceptibility reactions (A), may serve*
219 *as practical selection criteria. Alternatively, epidemiological processes that determine the speed and multiplication factor per*
220 *infection cycle (B) can be measured through repeated imaging. The effectiveness of this approach depends on the strength and*
221 *robustness of the genetic correlation between QR and its component traits (blue arrows). Illustrations of wheat plants were*
222 *modified from Schürch et al. (118).*

223 **Phenotypic detail.** Sensor-based phenotyping can generate insights into aspects of disease
224 that are impractical to obtain manually. A simple binary classification of host-pathogen
225 interactions overlooks that hypersensitive responses and other resistance or susceptibility
226 reactions are rarely uniform (94). A prominent example is tan spot of wheat, where different
227 isolates induce necrosis, chlorosis, or both depending on the combination of effectors and
228 susceptibility factors involved (48). Other examples include rice blast, where symptoms vary
229 from small necrotic spots to rapidly expanding lesions (86); wheat septoria tritici blotch, where
230 necrotic lesions can be surrounded by diffuse yellow halos or clearly delimited by dark brown
231 borders (7, 147), and fruiting body size and density can differ markedly (67, 110, 125) (Figure
232 1A); wheat brown rust, where pustules are sometimes surrounded by chlorosis, sometimes not
233 (Figure 1A); leaf spot on sugar beet, where lesions differ in the relative sizes of differently
234 colored sub-areas (71, 72); and Northern leaf blight on maize, where lesions display a variety
235 of shapes, sizes, and colors (91). A substantial genetic component is often evident (86, 91, 147),
236 indicating that detailed symptom analysis can provide valuable insights into the nature and
237 intensity of resistance or susceptibility reactions (7, 45, 72, 86).

238 Most studies of symptom phenotype focus on visible traits. While hyperspectral imaging can
239 enhance contrast, detect pre-visual symptoms, and detect subtle structural or biochemical
240 changes, its added value over RGB for characterizing host-pathogen interactions remains
241 unclear. Many hyperspectral studies rely on visible traits for model training (71, 72, 86), and
242 spectral signatures often reflect broad stress responses rather than specific host-pathogen
243 processes (e.g., 71, 86). Multi-modal benchmarking at identical resolution is needed to quantify
244 potential advantages, but the difficulty of generating an objective ‘ground truth’ and the
245 different amenability of types of sensor data to different data processing workflows (21)
246 complicate a direct comparison. The added value of higher spectral resolution for symptom
247 diagnosis and characterization must be clarified to guide future research.

248 **Temporal integration.** Repeated phenotyping facilitates monitoring of symptom
249 development over time, which is particularly useful in pathosystems involving apoplastic,
250 necrotrophic pathogens, where host responses to infection can be slower and more quantitative
251 (126). A well-studied case is the wheat resistance gene *Stb7*, which confers variable levels of
252 resistance to *Z. tritici* isolates carrying different variants of the matching effector (88). Although
253 this variation was uncovered using single end-point measurements, dynamic analyses could

254 help reveal underlying mechanisms. For example, lesion development rates have been linked
255 to resistance gene expression levels (19); end-point severity has been decomposed into
256 contributions from infection frequency, lesion expansion, and latency period duration (41) or
257 pustule number and pustule size (96); and the contribution of lesion expansion rates to field
258 epidemics has been quantified (9). Such studies often highlight how dynamic assessments can
259 uncover ‘more complex quantitative forms of resistance’ (41) beyond gene-for-gene
260 interactions. Yet, variation is sometimes traced back to major resistance genes (19, 88). Many
261 key variables influencing field-level QR are not present in controlled-environment assays (92,
262 93, 141). How QR traits measured under such conditions relate to the same traits in variable
263 field environments is often unclear, as is the relationship between specific QR components and
264 overall QR (9).

265 Organ-level monitoring of disease development under field conditions is technically
266 challenging due to greater scene variability (e.g., dynamic lighting) and complexity (e.g.,
267 multiple disorders), and because fixed imaging setups that ensure consistent positioning and
268 orientation of samples cannot be employed. Nevertheless, some reports of image-based in-field
269 dynamic assessments are available (9, 10). Improving robustness and throughput remain key
270 challenges and depend on the availability of benchmark datasets (8).

271 **Precision and accuracy.** Limitations of visual scorings in terms of accuracy and precision
272 have been extensively documented (28). Image processing algorithms, by applying a fixed set
273 of decision rules, act as fully objective evaluators, avoiding reproducibility issues (28).
274 However, this does not guarantee precision nor accuracy of the assessment. The risk of
275 systematic bias may exceed that of visual assessments unless algorithm performance has been
276 thoroughly validated across the full range of relevant scenarios (10, 67, 152). This is an
277 achievable objective under controlled conditions, provided clear boundary conditions are
278 defined. Still, algorithm development and validation are time-consuming, and gains in precision
279 and accuracy must clearly outweigh limitations imposed by other steps of the experimental
280 workflow, such as the inoculation procedure (57, 93).

281 **Perspectives for application.** Organ-level disease phenotyping enables characterization of
282 symptoms at a fine scale, allowing capture of both ‘static traits’ such as lesion shape, colour,
283 size, or edge properties, and ‘dynamic traits’ derived from time-series data, including lesion
284 expansion rates. However, concrete applications of such image-derived traits in breeding
285 remain poorly defined. One possibility is to exploit cases where symptom-level phenotypes are
286 strongly correlated with overall disease resistance (86). In such cases, easily scored lesion traits
287 could serve as secondary traits for indirect selection of QR (Figure 1A, 1C), avoiding challenges

288 associated with dynamic assessment of canopy-level QR (Figure 1C). This strategy is
289 particularly attractive in pathosystems where diverse gene-for-gene interactions converge on a
290 limited set of resistance or susceptibility reactions that produce characteristic symptom
291 phenotypes while strongly influencing overall disease resistance. Where static lesion traits
292 strongly correlate with dynamic traits, they could replace more costly time series measurements
293 (Figure 1A, 1B). This approach can be tested for lesion traits already known or newly
294 discovered from image-based phenotyping (9, 146).

295 Decomposing QR into mechanistic components (i.e., dynamic traits) and measuring their
296 responses to environmental factors such as relative humidity and temperature would improve
297 understanding of genotype-by-environment interactions in QR, aiding epidemiological
298 modelling and supporting management decisions through better predictions of seasonal
299 epidemics (3, 9). This is because components of QR that represent epidemiological processes
300 are at the bottom of the trait hierarchy, representing basic biological processes. Accordingly, in
301 analogy with a widely accepted paradigm in crop growth modelling (34), their dependency on
302 environmental variables can be assumed constant across environments.

303 Mechanistically deciphered components of resistance would also provide a basis for
304 pyramiding of functionally complementary resistance mechanisms (e.g., reduced infection
305 frequency with increased latency period and reduced lesion growth rate).

306 The effectiveness of indirect selection can be evaluated using the breeder's equation, and
307 this should be done early: Secondary traits for disease resistance are most useful when the
308 germplasm to select from is variable, trait heritability is high, genetic correlations with overall
309 resistance are strong, and assessment costs are low enough to support large-scale screening and
310 a high selection intensity (60, 134). In addition, secondary traits would be useful in
311 pathosystems characterized by diverse and fast-evolving pathogen populations and highly
312 polygenic host-pathogen interactions, but less useful where less diversity is present and
313 relatively few genes dominate interactions. In the latter pathosystems, development of
314 molecular markers is preferable. At present, these ideas remain largely aspirational, and visual
315 field scoring remains the dominant practice.

316 **Field-based phenotyping of pathogen-plant interactions**

317 **Measurement strategies.** Field evaluations are required for reliable assessment of canopy-
318 level QR, as polycyclic epidemics and their drivers cannot be adequately reproduced under
319 controlled conditions (93, 94, 141). Field evaluations usually follow two complementary
320 approaches. Under artificial inoculation, the targeted disease typically dominates, producing
321 characteristic symptoms and synchronized disease development that is comparably easy to

322 score. Such trials provide a robust estimate of genetic resistance if the inoculum is
 323 representative of natural pathogen populations. In contrast, natural infections are often
 324 characterized by more subtle differences between genotypes, asynchronous and spatially
 325 heterogenous disease development, and co-occurrence of multiple diseases at comparable
 326 intensities. In natural infections, disease expression is influenced significantly by escape
 327 mechanisms and genotype-by-environment interactions. These conditions require more
 328 sensitive, specific, and robust assessment methods, as well as spatially and temporally explicit
 329 quantification of disease to capture relevant variation in disease progression.

330 Although visual scoring remains widely used, it faces even greater limitations in accuracy,
 331 precision, and throughput at the plot scale than at the single organ scale. Implicit integration
 332 across multiple biological scales (from symptoms to organs, plants, vegetation fractions, and
 333 plots) introduces subjectivity, while limited throughput reduces the number of candidate
 334 genotypes that can be evaluated. Together with the lack of standardization that complicates
 335 estimation of genotypic value across environments, these factors reduce genetic gain for QR
 336 (13, 117). Repeated assessments are typically required to achieve a satisfactory level of
 337 precision and capture important rank changes over time. These challenges motivate the need
 338 for high-throughput, season-long, canopy-level assessments, which entails numerous additional
 339 challenges discussed below and illustrated in Figure 2.

340
 341 *Figure 2 Seven key challenges in high-throughput image-based disease diagnosis and quantification in the field. (A) Many*
 342 *diseases develop gradually as a function of genotypic and environmental factors, and epidemic development is closely related*
 343 *to quantitative resistance (QR). Data acquisition must be interaction-free and compatible with evolving canopies. Manual*
 344 *image acquisition protocols can support method development, but must allow transfer to autonomous platforms. (B) Data*
 345 *processing must be robust across growth stages and scene complexity, enabling reliable background removal and extraction of*
 346 *relevant organs. (C) Images must balance resolution for symptom-level diagnosis with adequate sampling area for canopy-*
 347 *level severity estimation. (D) Localizing symptoms within the three-dimensional canopy (e.g., leveraging co-registered depth*
 348 *maps) increases value for downstream analyses. Illustrations of wheat plants were modified from Schürch et al. (118).*

349 **Interaction-free data acquisition.** To achieve high throughput, disease severity must be
 350 assessed directly at the canopy level, avoiding destructive sampling or similar labour-intensive

351 measurements. Therefore, remote sensing approaches capturing canopy-level signals have been
352 widely proposed (5, 29). These methods generally work satisfactorily in simplified scenarios
353 (e.g., detection of MGR with a few diagnostic inoculated strains), but extending them to field
354 evaluations of QR under natural infection is highly challenging due to morphological,
355 structural, and phenological diversity of cereal canopies, co-occurrence of other stresses, and
356 varying agronomic practices which confound disease-related signals (5, 89).

357 High-resolution RGB imaging of sampled plant material can facilitate reliable disease
358 diagnosis and measurement of field-level QR, but is labor-intensive and has required stringent
359 image standardization until recently. The advent of DL has relaxed many of these requirements
360 (65, 75, 152), speeding up data acquisition, and even enabling repeated assessment of the same
361 leaves in situ (9, 10). However, a clear separation between foreground and background is
362 typically required, meaning that single organs have to be properly exposed and oriented with
363 respect to the imaging device. This introduces subjectivity and represents a complex and time-
364 consuming operation that contradicts throughput requirements.

365 Segmentation of individual plants or organs without direct interaction is feasible in crops
366 such as sugar beet (54) but is difficult in dense cereal canopies. For many applications, a
367 severity metric at the vegetation fraction level is sufficient, though this still requires plant-
368 background and organ segmentation as well as identification of the image area suitable for
369 analysis to relate detected symptoms to the total visible susceptible tissue (11, 59, 153). Prompt-
370 based approaches have been proposed (128, 143), but human-computer interaction during
371 inference is impractical for large datasets, and proposed work-arounds are not applicable for
372 images of dense canopies that rarely allow reliable foreground-background separation. Zenkl
373 et al. (153) addressed this by combining texture analysis with depth estimation to identify in-
374 focus image regions, coupled with organ segmentation to quantify susceptible tissue. This
375 approach enabled interaction-free severity estimation much faster than leaf-by-leaf approaches
376 (153). Focus-bracketing can further increase the leaf area analyzed without a corresponding
377 increase in time used for data acquisition (151).

378 **Scene variability and complexity.** Time-resolved phenotyping to capture epidemics
379 requires robust data acquisition and processing (Figure 2A-C). Robustness in this context
380 requires (i) flexible adjustment of sensor position, orientation, and exposure to ensure consistent
381 imaging of comparable vegetation elements despite variation in canopy height and three-
382 dimensional structure (Figure 2A); (ii) sufficient scene understanding to reliably identify plants
383 and their organs across growth stages and distinguish them from background elements such as
384 soil, sky, or residues (Figure 2B), and (iii) the ability to detect and segment disease symptoms

385 in images captured under variable and complex illumination (Figure 2C). Meeting these
386 requirements depends critically on the availability of training data with balanced sampling
387 across growth stages, lighting conditions, genotypes, and environments.

388 The need for such training data has been widely recognized for tasks such as plant-
389 background segmentation (79) and organ segmentation (139). While the need for comparable
390 datasets in disease phenotyping is increasingly recognized, most currently available large
391 datasets span multiple crops, encompass diverse imaging scenarios, and show substantial
392 variability in image and annotation quality and detail (e.g., 142). To maximize the usefulness
393 of models for quantitative disease assessments, focus should be placed on generating diverse
394 but crop-specific datasets with comprehensive, highly precise symptom-level annotations. It is
395 critical that failure cases are detected, curated, and iteratively incorporated into such data sets
396 to sustain robustness as models are deployed beyond their calibration domains. This continuous
397 effort is expensive, while plant phenotyping is a small market and each disease within each crop
398 represents an even smaller market share.

399 Data scarcity is a pervasive issue in DL for plant phenotyping, and reducing the need for
400 manually curated training data at minimal performance loss is an active field of research (132).
401 Proposed solutions include synthetic data generation, domain adaptation, and, more recently,
402 the leveraging of foundation models for vision tasks (132). A wheat-specific foundation model
403 pre-trained with 2.5 million high-resolution images consistently outperformed models pre-
404 trained on general-domain data sets when fine-tuned on comparably small data sets for specific
405 vision tasks typical of field-phenotyping (55). Whether these approaches will similarly benefit
406 disease phenotyping at the macro-scale remains to be explored.

407 **Multiple disorders and symptom variability.** Biotic and abiotic stresses commonly co-
408 occur, creating multiple visible disorders. To avoid systematic bias in the assessment of one
409 disease due to the presence of other disorders, individual symptoms must be reliably diagnosed,
410 and this diagnosis must be achieved based on single-shot images, as tracking individual lesions
411 over time in an interaction-free manner remains largely unavailable.

412 RGB-based diagnosis is feasible when an expert can confidently diagnose symptoms through
413 visual inspection, provided images capture the visual cues with sufficient quality and context
414 (20). However, image-based diagnosis is often evaluated on datasets with a single disease per
415 image, at stages when symptoms are very prominent, typical, and visible on specific
416 photographed organs (63, 102, 104, 119, 130). This can lead to an overestimation of the
417 technology's readiness for practical field application. In reality, multiple disorders often co-
418 occur in the same images, and symptoms display a wide range of appearances related to their

419 age, host and pathogen genotypes, spatial context, and environmental conditions. Based on our
420 own experience (10, 152), mixed infections can be handled by computer vision algorithms in
421 cereal pathosystems, but symptom appearance can vary largely according to symptom age,
422 particularly in rusts, where emerging pustules progress from pre-rupture to ruptured and
423 sporulating, to discharged uredinia or telia. Since different diseases can be prevalent at different
424 times and new symptoms can appear continuously, the full range of symptom stages can be
425 present at any time and must be accurately diagnosed. Generating the necessary training data
426 could benefit from image time series with symptom tracking (8).

427 In these complex scenarios, diagnosis must be achieved at the symptom-level, including for
428 disorders not caused by pathogens. A prime example is leaf tip necrosis associated with the
429 quantitative resistance gene *Lr34* in wheat. Mis-diagnosing this host-driven necrosis as a biotic
430 stress symptom represents a worst-case scenario, because it would lead to selection against a
431 valuable source of resistance. This adds complexity for both models and human annotators,
432 making symptom-level diagnosis far more challenging than image-level classification. It
433 requires a multi-level decision within the diagnostic image processing workflow and a data-
434 centric rather than a model-centric approach with high-quality training data (109).

435 Diseases with systemic symptoms require capturing broader spatial contexts for correct
436 diagnosis. Examples include viral infections causing general yellowing and stunted or delayed
437 growth, or root pathogens such as *Gaeumannomyces graminis tritici* causing dead wheat culms
438 but distinguishable from fusarium head blight if the entire plant is imaged to reveal that stems
439 and leaves are necrotic as well. Similarly, detection and segmentation of wilted sorghum leaves,
440 and correct damage attribution to sorghum charcoal root rot requires images with sufficient
441 spatial context (52).

442 A central open question is whether a higher spectral resolution could significantly improve
443 single-shot symptom diagnosis in cases where neither color nor spatial context from RGB
444 imagery is sufficient. In theory, hyperspectral imaging could provide additional discriminatory
445 power (81). Systematic evaluation of which spectral ranges or derived indices offer consistent
446 gains in diagnostic accuracy, and whether these can be translated into practical protocols for
447 breeding likely depends on simultaneous imaging using different sensor modalities and co-
448 registration of the resulting images as a basis for conducting such comparisons (37, 59).

449 **Data aggregation.** Symptom-level diagnosis in many cereal pathosystems requires very
450 high spatial resolution. For example, reliable detection of *Septoria tritici* blotch fruiting bodies
451 requires ~0.03 mm per pixel (125, 152). At this scale, each image captures only a small portion
452 of an experimental unit and many single-image-based measurements must be aggregated to

453 obtain precise phenotype estimates, similar to traditional leaf sampling. Aggregation is
454 especially important in pathosystems with unevenly distributed symptoms (e.g., splash- or
455 smear-dispersed infections), but is complicated by auto-correlation across repeated
456 measurements (151) and the need to assign values to different parts of plants or canopies to
457 account for their variable importance for yield formation (e.g., vertical leaf layers (33); Figure
458 2D).

459 **ESCAPE**

460 **Candidate traits and measurement strategies**

461 Disease escape occurs when plants avoid infection not through resistance, but via genetically
462 determined traits that reduce direct physical contact between the pathogen and susceptible host
463 tissues (100, 103, 141). Common escape traits include plant morphology and the resulting
464 canopy architecture, leaf surface traits, and phenology (94, 103, 106, 141). Despite their
465 importance, sometimes explaining 50% of the genotypic variance in disease severity (74), these
466 mechanisms remain poorly characterized overall (103, 141), limiting ideotype development.

467 Many morphological, structural, leaf surface, and phenological traits are highly heritable in
468 cereals and have been exploited by breeders. This indicates potential for further improvements,
469 though modifications may involve important trade-offs with other agronomic constraints (32).

470 Plant morphology and canopy architecture influence epidemics by altering microclimate and
471 spore deposition, dispersal, and interception within the canopy (94, 106). A common example
472 is the association between plant height and disease: for splash-dispersed pathogens this mainly
473 reflects effects on spore movement and interception (1, 14, 106), whereas for wind-dispersed
474 pathogens it largely reflects height-induced microclimatic changes affecting infection and
475 disease development (93). Plant height may also be a proxy for other architectural traits such
476 as canopy density and vertical leaf layering and overlap that interact with other traits such as
477 leaf insertion angle, curvature, and length to determine the distance between infectious lesions
478 and new leaves, influencing the vertical spread of secondary inoculum (77, 107) while shaping
479 the penetration of light, rain drops, and air flow within the canopy, which in turn affects
480 pathogen survival, growth, and infection success.

481 Phenology also strongly interacts with disease. Late-maturing genotypes are often more
482 resistant than early-maturing ones (110, 133). However, it is often unclear whether observed
483 associations arise from genetic linkage, pleiotropy, or represent true phenological escape.
484 Sometimes, they may simply reflect biases introduced by assessing disease severity at a fixed
485 point in time without accounting for differences in crop developmental stage (14, 42, 66, 133).

486 A direct assessment of escape and its separation from genetic resistance can be impractical,
487 as it would require quantifying both the number of spore penetration attempts (reduced by
488 escape) and their success rate (reduced by resistance). As an alternative, some studies corrected
489 disease severity for the effect of already known escape traits related to phenology, plant height,
490 and vertical leaf layering (14). To estimate the relative contributions of resistance and escape,
491 variance in disease severity explained by possible escape traits was compared with variance
492 explained by the presence of major resistance genes. A more holistic estimate of escape,
493 agnostic both to specific escape traits and the genetic architecture of resistance, could be
494 obtained by comparing a genotype's performance under natural epidemics with its level of
495 genetic resistance estimated under artificial inoculations that minimize the influence of escape
496 traits (110, 124).

497 Assessing escape and unravelling underlying mechanisms requires specific phenotypic data.
498 First, contrasting management and environmental conditions must be included, emphasizing
499 the importance of measurement throughput to enable this expansion in scope. Second, many
500 observed or postulated escape effects are spatial; accordingly, their validation requires spatially
501 explicit measurement of disease, e.g., across different leaf layers in a canopy. Third,
502 phenotyping should simultaneously capture disease and candidate escape traits related to
503 morphology, architecture, and phenology (14). Fourth, both escape and disease-related traits
504 should be evaluated dynamically rather than as end-point values. For example, stem or
505 internode elongation may be more relevant to disease escape than final plant height and vertical
506 leaf layering in the fully established canopy (76, 77, 106). Finally, measurements must span
507 extended periods and be robust to associated variability.

508 **Phenotyping of candidate escape-related traits and spatial disease occurrence**

509 Quantitative characterization of canopy architecture and plant morphology relies on accurate
510 three-dimensional representations of organs, plants, and canopies, typically derived from depth
511 maps, or explicitly represented as point clouds, voxels, or surface meshes. Such representations
512 provide the basis for estimating structural traits at plot-level (e.g., canopy height, volume, or
513 leaf angle distribution), and at plant- and organ-level (e.g., leaf shape, size, curvature, and
514 insertion angle, internode length, or ear volume, shape, and orientation). Extracting meaningful
515 traits from raw 3D data typically requires point cloud segmentation for plant and organ
516 identification, geometric fitting, and surface reconstruction (15, 17, 56, 61, 150, 154), with
517 methods often tailored to crop architecture and phenotyping goals (56, 105, 148).

518 Field-based 3D phenotyping presents a series of specific technical challenges: dense
519 canopies cause occlusion and self-shading; uniform canopies present few visually distinctive

520 features that can be used as tie points for 3D reconstruction; variable ambient illumination,
521 wind-induced motion, and the need for high throughput constrains sensor options. When high-
522 quality 3D data are obtained, trait extraction remains challenging due primarily to overlap,
523 incomplete visibility of plants and organs, and a lack of annotated data sets that can be used for
524 method development (18, 150).

525 Despite these challenges, significant progress has been made for several major field crops.
526 A pragmatic approach is to estimate canopy cover, above-ground biomass, and plant height
527 using Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) (64). RGB-based structure from motion and multi-
528 view stereo approaches are particularly well suited for large-scale application under field
529 conditions due to their robustness to ambient illumination and ability to generate highly
530 detailed, texturized 3D reconstructions (17, 39, 43, 61, 142, 154). Structure-from-motion
531 approaches based on UAV RGB imagery have been extensively validated across diverse
532 environments and crop species, demonstrating high accuracy and robustness in tracking canopy
533 height development (25, 111, 113), allowing an effective capture of this important dynamic
534 component of spatial escape. A robotic system equipped with multiple 2-camera stereo vision
535 setups allowed extraction of plot-level architectural traits such as canopy volume and plant
536 surface area, as well as plant level traits such as leaf angle, in sorghum and maize (17, 142).

537 Dense 3D reconstruction of crop canopies based on multi-view imaging has advanced
538 considerably by complementing traditional approaches based on key point matching and
539 triangulation with learned 3D representations (15, 43, 61, 145, 154). Some of these new
540 approaches learn to estimate depth from a single image (144), while others can jointly predict
541 all geometric aspects of a scene (including camera positions, depth, and 3D structure) without
542 relying on explicit feature matching (138). These developments significantly improve
543 reconstruction accuracy in complex crop canopies where repetitive textures and occlusions
544 often limit traditional methods, but these outputs eventually have to be converted to explicit 3D
545 representations such as point clouds or meshes for trait extraction. Extracting high-precision
546 plant-level morphological traits, particularly for deeper canopy layers, remains challenging in
547 dense stands and may require physical interaction to open crop rows and thin plants within rows
548 at image acquisition.

549 Similar datasets can support tracking of phenological development. For example, the
550 beginning and end of stem elongation can be estimated based on direct measurements of canopy
551 height (68, 113) or indirectly via multi-view ground cover estimates (112); heading and
552 flowering stages can be estimated based on inflorescence detection in a timeseries of high-
553 resolution RGB images (115); senescence and ripening can be estimated based on color

554 properties of plant organs and their dynamics (11). The combination of structural features such
555 as height and high-resolution RGB imagery may further improve phenology inference (112).
556 However, these approaches primarily capture biophysical growth or major, visually discernable
557 morphological or biochemical changes in plants, which serve as proxies for phenological
558 transitions rather than providing a direct measurement (40).

559 Precisely localizing disease in 3D canopies involves mapping detected lesions onto 3D
560 canopy representations. Ideally, each symptom would be assigned to a specific leaf on a specific
561 plant, capturing both its vertical position in the canopy profile and its position within the plant's
562 hierarchical structure (76, 77, 106). This can be done by segmenting lesions directly in 3D
563 models (108) or by projecting lesions detected in 2D views onto reconstructed 3D canopies
564 (135, 154). However, this requires identifying all organs, assigning them to a specific individual
565 plant (topology) and determining their arrangement within that plant (phyllotaxy). This is
566 particularly difficult in dense canopies and would require the entire plant to be fully represented,
567 which is in conflict with the high spatial resolution imaging needed to support symptom
568 diagnosis.

569 A pragmatic approach could combine disease phenotyping from appropriate view angles
570 with co-registered depth information to enable approximation of the affected leaf layer and the
571 position of detected symptoms relative to the soil, the top leaf, and, potentially, the canopy light
572 penetration gradient. A proof-of-concept of such an approach was demonstrated by Zenkl et al.
573 (153), who combined monocular depth estimation with image texture analysis to identify
574 focused regions in images with a very shallow depth of field. Although their side-view imaging
575 setup did not allow estimation of the vertical position of detected symptoms within the canopy,
576 this limitation could be addressed by adopting a nadir or an oblique top-down imaging geometry
577 in combination with methods to expose lower canopy layers (c.f. Figure 2A).

578 **From candidate traits to mechanistic understanding**

579 The outcome of pathogen-plant interactions emerges from complex, dynamic interactions
580 between a changing canopy, a pathogen population, and a fluctuating environment (50, 121).
581 As pointed out by Simko et al. (121), modelling is essential to 'sieve through' this complexity,
582 as measurement alone can be insufficient. For example, identifying genotypes with strong
583 escape characteristics is of limited value if the underlying mechanisms cannot be identified to
584 derive ideotypes. Functional-structural plant models, originally developed to study light
585 interception and canopy-level photosynthesis resulting from the dynamic interaction between
586 the canopy and its environment (47), offer a powerful framework to mechanistically link plant
587 morphology, canopy architecture, microclimate, and disease development. Some studies have

588 employed them to simulate key spatial-temporal processes involved in canopy-level epidemics,
 589 such as spore dispersal within the canopy (50, 51, 106, 136). These approaches have
 590 demonstrated potential for investigating the role of cultivar morphology and canopy
 591 architecture in determining the course of an epidemic (106, 121, 123). Unfortunately, the
 592 availability of ‘real data’ from field experiments that can be used to structure, parameterize, and
 593 validate such models has been extremely limited.

594 Field phenomics has been proposed as a natural complement to epidemiological modelling
 595 to address this limitation (121). Data collected at high spatial and temporal resolution at the leaf
 596 and canopy levels could help define the structure of simulation models in a more data-driven
 597 way, as has been done for the 3D plant models themselves (2) (Supplementary Figure 2). For
 598 example, non-destructive, dynamic estimates of height, leaf area index, leaf angles, leaf
 599 layering, and senescence patterns can be obtained, while spatially explicit disease maps would
 600 enable capture of lateral and vertical progression of disease, as outlined above.

601 Thus, combining these datasets could guide the development of models by (i) identifying
 602 which variables and interactions should be considered in modelling disease progression, (ii)
 603 providing biologically meaningful parameter values, and (iii) enabling model calibration and
 604 validation on a broad data basis to better reflect observed reality (Supplementary Figure 2).
 605 Bridging the gap between models and phenomics should support a paradigm shift from a
 606 gradual stochastic to a more ideotype-driven approach based on detailed, mechanistic
 607 understanding of pathosystems.

608
 609 *Supplementary Figure 2 Potential synergies between field phenomics and functional-structural plant modelling for advancing*
 610 *mechanistic understanding of disease epidemics in the field. (A) Image sequence of a diseased leaf showing detected and*
 611 *segmented symptoms alongside model-simulated progression for the same pathosystems. (B) High-resolution RGB image and*
 612 *corresponding monocular depth estimation from a state-of-the-art model. Integrating such depth maps with symptom detection*
 613 *and segmentation enables spatially explicit characterization of disease within the three-dimensional canopy. (C) Time-resolved*
 614 *phenotypic data at the organ- or canopy-level can inform the structure, parameterization, calibration, and validation of*

615 *epidemiological models. Iterative feedback (circular red arrows) between field observations and model simulations will refine*
616 *model accuracy and support the development of an accurate and detailed mechanistic understanding of observed disease*
617 *phenotypes. Right-hand panels of Figures (A) and (B) were adapted from Garin et al. (50, 51), Annals of Botany, by permission*
618 *of Oxford University Press.*

619 **TOLERANCE**

620 **Candidate traits and measurement strategies**

621 Tolerance reflects both constitutive and adaptive traits that help maintain source capacity
622 under infection. Adaptive mechanisms include an upregulation of photosynthesis in healthy
623 tissue, re-growth, enhanced remobilization, and delayed senescence (26, 92). Constitutive traits
624 include a large canopy ensuring a high initial source:sink ratio, larger stem reserves, and canopy
625 architectures that provide favorable light distribution and a high radiation interception
626 efficiency (26, 92).

627 Dynamic compensation is central to yield formation and stability in cereals, as losses in one
628 yield component can be offset by adjustments in others throughout much of the growing season.
629 Taking the example of wheat, poor plant emergence can be compensated by more fertile tillers,
630 fewer tillers by more grains per ear, and fewer grains by higher individual grain weight (122).
631 Depending on their timing and severity, diseases can impair any yield formation process,
632 thereby impacting any yield component (Figure 3A, 3B). Despite this, studies on tolerance
633 rarely link disease intensity to phenology and individual yield components; instead, seasonal
634 integrals of disease severity are typically linked to end-of-season grain yield (26, 98). This is
635 notable given the large differences in how different yield formation processes, occurring at
636 different developmental stages, respond to reductions in resource availability, and the varying
637 potential to subsequently compensate these losses (26, 31, 35, 116). A mechanistic
638 understanding of tolerance, which is necessary for its targeted optimization, requires temporally
639 resolved data on disease intensity, crop phenology, and yield components (Figure 3A, 3B).

640 Empirical evidence for constitutive and adaptive traits that influence yield response to
641 disease and could serve as selection criteria remains scarce. Few studies linked tolerance to
642 candidate constitutive canopy or plant traits (36, 46) and even fewer to adaptive traits such as
643 leaf senescence dynamics (11, 16). This gap likely reflects the prohibitive effort associated with
644 detailed, season-long field phenotyping of disease, phenology, yield components, and candidate
645 tolerance-conferring traits using traditional methods.

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Figure 3 Tolerance characterization should combine growth-stage specific measurement of disease with monitoring of yield formation and phenology. (A) Examples of phenology and yield components estimated using field phenomics. (B) Epidemics for two contrasting genotypes (G1 and G2; dashed lines) measured from emergence to maturity. Phenology and coincidence of certain growth stages and yield formation processes with disease may differ across genotypes, resulting in different yield components being affected to varying degrees (circles and arrows). (C) Two example concepts for a phenomics-enabled search strategy for growth-stage specific tolerance, with images illustrating the nature of the required phenotypic data. Left: In spring, healthy plots maintain full greenness (solid lines), whereas diseased plots show necrosis (dashed lines). These differences affect ear fertility (i.e., grains per ear), as exemplified by ear images. The degree of impact reflects phase-specific tolerance. The mechanistic determinant of tolerance is elusive in this example, but could result from a large leaf area index or high biomass to maintain source capacity. Right: Between flowering and harvest, disease reduces the integral under the greenness curve (dashed lines) compared to a healthy plot (solid black line), affecting grain filling. The degree of impact reflects phase-specific tolerance. Greenness dynamics are influenced in two ways: i) a direct effect reducing canopy greenness during the stay-green phase (pink arrow); and ii) an interaction between disease and senescence. Disease may accelerate (blue dashed line), not affect (purple dashed line), or delay (green dashed line) senescence, within the leaf fraction and in other organ fractions (stems, ears). In this model, accelerated senescence is a mechanistic determinant of sensitivity, whereas delayed senescence is a mechanistic determinant of tolerance, if associated with increased rate or duration of grain filling. Illustrations of wheat plants were modified from Schürch et al. (118).

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Tolerance is commonly quantified as the slope of the relationship between disease intensity and yield, where disease intensity is typically expressed as area under the disease progress curve. Variation needed to estimate this relationship is often obtained by pooling data across sites and years, particularly when the absolute size of healthy and diseased leaf area is used to estimate tolerance (98). However, because environmental factors are typically confounded with disease occurrence and severity, a gradient of damage within a specific environment may

670 ultimately be required to isolate disease-related effects. For example, septoria epidemics are
671 more common under conditions of low light, excess rainfall, and low temperatures, which
672 reduce crop performance even in the absence of disease (127).

673 Some authors have proposed estimating tolerance based on traits measured in healthy crops
674 (i.e., constitutive traits) (16, 36), or through controlled manipulations of the source-sink balance
675 which mimic disease effects, such as partial defoliation. Indeed, such experimental approaches
676 have long been used to better understand sink- or source-related constraints at various growth
677 stages (31). We believe that disease gradients, generated through differential inoculation or
678 fungicide treatments, can become a practical approach for source:sink manipulation, as in-field
679 quantitative and spatially explicit measurements of disease become more accurate, high-
680 throughput, and scalable.

681 **Phenotyping concepts for capturing tolerance and identifying tolerance-conferring** 682 **traits**

683 Based on the above considerations, we propose a two-tiered phenotyping strategy for
684 tolerance, where the primary objective is to implement high-throughput disease progression
685 monitoring along with phenology tracking (Figure 3A, 3B). In combination with an end-of-
686 season assessment of yield components and in-season monitoring of yield formation processes
687 (Figure 3A), such data will allow season-level aggregate measures of tolerance to be
688 decomposed into sub-components that reveal how productivity is affected at specific growth
689 stages. Once this has been achieved, the secondary objective should be to identify both
690 constitutive and adaptive traits as mechanistic determinants of phase-specific tolerance in
691 support of trait-based selection. Two example concepts implementing this proposed strategy for
692 wheat are illustrated in Figure 3C.

693 **Disease phenotyping.** Tolerance characterization may allow certain relaxations compared
694 with phenotyping for QR and escape. First, symptom-level diagnosis may be less critical, as
695 tolerance to foliar diseases represents primarily a plant's ability to maintain productivity under
696 a given level of damage in terms of the loss of photosynthetic capacity (26, 141). A broad
697 differentiation among damage types may remain necessary, however: biotrophic and
698 necrotrophic pathogens affect plant metabolism and canopy function in distinct ways, and
699 abiotic stress and physiological symptoms must still be discriminated from pathogen-induced
700 damage. Second, the spatial resolution and damage attribution to plant organs in the 3D canopy
701 is less stringent, as the primary interest lies in quantifying overall damage to the crop, e.g., the
702 total plant photosynthetic area as seen from outside of the plot.

703 In contrast, relative assessments of healthy and diseased area as typically used for resistance
704 characterization deliver an incomplete picture. An exact, high-throughput measurement of leaf
705 area index (LAI) in dense canopies is likely to remain a significant challenge due primarily to
706 occlusion, even given further progress in 3D reconstruction of dense canopies. A precise,
707 intermediate-throughput assessment of LAI could be achieved by combining non-destructive
708 in-field leaf area measurements based on RGB images of single leaves (10) with image-based
709 plot-level tiller or ear counts.

710 **Yield component phenotyping.** Plant density estimates are readily achievable in crops with
711 larger inter-plant distances and precise placement of single seeds, such as maize or sugar beet.
712 In wheat and other crops with a similar growth habit and canopy structure, plant density
713 estimates may be based on leaf-tip detection at emergence (73), but this approach is complicated
714 by the fact that emergence of second leaves on some plants may overlap with emergence of first
715 leaves on later-germinating plants. Evaluation of greenness maxima in multi-view images may
716 provide an alternative approach applicable at later growth stages (112), which may be useful
717 especially in winter cereals to correct for differences in winter survival. Fertile tiller density can
718 be estimated by detecting spikes visible in 2D canopy images (80), but accuracy can be
719 improved using multi-view information aggregated through explicit 3D reconstruction (154).
720 Several yield components such as average grain weight and grains per planted area can be
721 determined at plot-level after harvest by combining simple image analysis with total grain
722 weight. The average number of grains per spike, and the average number of spikes per plant
723 can then be derived.

724 The most difficult yield components to assess are the number of spikelets per spike and the
725 number of grains per spikelet. Some works have successfully segmented spikelets in ear images
726 captured under controlled conditions (95). In principle, the same can be achieved directly from
727 high-resolution RGB imagery captured under field conditions. A complicating factor is that
728 spikes must be fully visible and properly oriented toward the camera, which may introduce
729 sampling bias. This bias may be alleviated if multi-view approaches are adopted to reduce
730 occlusion (154) and increase the portion of ears meeting these criteria. A direct image-based
731 assessment of the number of grains per spikelet is not possible as grains remain enclosed within
732 the glumes, lemmas, and paleae of the spikelets.

733 Where a ‘stress free’ reference treatment or a gradient in disease is available for each
734 genotype under study, the combination of in-field and post-harvest assessment of yield
735 components and their comparison across treatments can reveal the effect of a stressor on
736 different yield formation processes for that genotype.

737 **Phenotyping candidate tolerance traits.** Most amenable to high-throughput phenotyping are
738 constitutive or adaptive traits related to biophysical growth and phenological plasticity.
739 Although traits that can be directly and mechanistically linked with tolerance can be difficult to
740 measure, reasonable proxies are readily accessible. For example, early vigour can be
741 approximated by canopy cover growth or canopy height development (53). This can be a proxy
742 for the timing of leaf emergence, leaf elongation rate, phyllochron, and tillering which can
743 impact the relationship between the growth of the canopy and the development of the epidemic
744 (107). Compensation via plasticity in yield component formation can also be quantified (see
745 above). This would be useful in cases where disease is more prominent during a specific growth
746 stage, impairing a specific yield formation process. Potential passive effects of diseases or
747 actively regulated adjustments of senescence in response to disease can be readily observed
748 based on colour properties of plant organs and their dynamics (6, 11). Compensation may occur
749 through modified senescence dynamics in disease-affected organs (leaves; organ-level
750 compensation) as well as in non-affected organs (e.g., stems, ears; plant-level compensation).

751 **CONCLUSIONS AND THE WAY FORWARD**

752 Image-based phenomics can support mechanistic understanding of a crop's robustness to
753 disease by enabling quantitative assessment of resistance, escape, and tolerance in relation to
754 canopy structure, growth, phenology, and yield formation. Organ- and symptom-level
755 assessments provide mechanistic insights and may yield useful secondary traits for indirect
756 selection, while canopy-level evaluations under field conditions directly capture overall
757 performance in realistic environments. Challenges include robust imaging across variable
758 canopy architectures and illumination, symptom-level diagnosis under heterogeneous
759 conditions, and biologically meaningful aggregation of high-resolution measurements to
760 experimental units. Gaps persist in creation of broad training datasets, standardization of
761 acquisition protocols, and integration of disease data with complementary crop phenotyping
762 and modeling to link disease development to yield and quality.

763 To make image-based phenotyping actionable for breeding, variety testing, and crop
764 management, research should focus on developing scalable, interaction-free data acquisition
765 protocols, high-quality annotated datasets, and robust methods for symptom detection,
766 segmentation, and aggregation. Integrating disease phenotyping with 3D canopy
767 reconstruction, phenology monitoring, and epidemiological and functional-structural plant
768 modeling will enable mechanistic interpretation of epidemics and prediction of their impact on

769 yield and quality. This approach can provide the mechanistic understanding required for data-
770 driven ideotype design and trait-based selection.

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